

**Awesome repetition of number 3 in correction of *Trimorphic*
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**Awesome repetition of number 3 in correction of *Trimorphic* Extreme
Clubfoot Deformities by *Triple* Surgical Skin Expansion
(An Evolutionary, Multifaceted, Scientific Perspective)**

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Abstract

Author, a passionate researcher in Clubfoot, since over half a century, published an article on trimorphic extreme clubfoot deformities <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00264-017-3741-6>, in International Orthopaedics (SICOT) in 2018. This was original research in this grey area, prevalent in LMICs with more than 80 % global population. AIM: Continuing in similar vein, author was motivated to write this unique article with certain “believe-it-or-not” events, under three headings: **FIRSTLY**; many things are destined to happen in nature at a fixed time and place. This research, happening pointedly at Patiala, is another such event.

HOW and WHY of this, are given in PREFACE and INTRODUCTION of author’s Clubfoot Book [57]. **SECONDLY**: unprecedented, 20 repetitions of number 3 in any research, besides five in personal life and **THIRDLY**, on Google search, number 3 in numerology, symbolic of planet Jupiter, has innumerable good attributes for the related people. This number has also been found to have, since ancient times, myriad unbelievable, evolutionary bonds, in every area of humanity, on planet earth and beyond; which are scientific, spiritual, socio- religious, political etc. **MATERIAL** has been derived from the contents of author’s clubfoot research and **METHODS** have been Google Search, daily living human activities and author’s experience. **CONCLUSIONS**: 1. Many events are completely scientific; 2. Others are unique coincidences with scientific explanation and 3. Still others are amazing truths, proving once again veracity of famous quote “Truth is Stranger than Fiction”. Because of its uniqueness, this article does need a loud awakening call, to spread its wings.

Keywords: Number 3 repetitions; Trimorphic clubfoot deformities; Triple surgical Skin expansion; Multifaceted perspective in trimorphic clubfeet; Clubfoot and numerology number 3; 3-in-1 surgical concept in clubfoot; Jupiter and number 3; Human psyche and number 3 in clubfoot

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Introduction

Considering the nature of subject, I will start, a little differently, with, 3 PARTS, Sanskrit Indian Vedic prayer. I hear its *echo* constantly, in this research:- असतो मा सद्गमय । तमसो मा ज्योतर्गमय । मृत्योमाग अमृतं र्मय । ॐ
Translated to English, this means: "O" lord, lead me from falsehood to truth, darkness (of ignorance) to light (of knowledge), death (weaknesses of life) to immortality (strengths of life), AUM- peace,; peace, peace. Reciting this prayer purifies your mind, energises your body and gives peace for good work, because of intimate Body-Mind relationship.

Material and Methods

A comprehensive study of number 3 can be divided in to two distinct parts:-

1. Number 3 in General
2. As Related to Clubfoot Research

1. Number 3 in General

This is the most important number in numerology, with enormous material, pervading through every areas of human existence: all branches of science, medical and non-medical: physics, chemistry, biology, pharmaceuticals, trigonometry, cosmology, economics, mathematics, nanotechnology, environmental, psychology, sociology, yoga, spirituality, religions, politics/ governance and all daily living activities, from birth till death. An extensive search of Google and author's own experience *has unearthed enormous material in diverse fields* [1-51]:

A: Scientific basis: [1-7]

1. Number 3 is the whole as shown in the three eras of time: Past, Present and Future.
2. *Theory of relativity of Einstein* is based on 3 things: Mass, Length and Time.
3. Newton's three laws of MOTION: inertia, acceleration and reaction;
4. There are 3 forms of matter: solid, liquid and gas.
5. Three particles of atom: electron, proton and neutron.
6. Triangle is strongest basic shape and all others are its multiples. It has strong applications in trigonometry, physics, architecture, engineering and many others.
7. Human biology: Tripod gait is a stable gait for physically handicapped. Three major parts of brain: cerebrum, cerebellum and brain stem.
8. Three phases of life: Birth, sustenance & death.
9. Three states of human consciousness: awakened, dream and deep sleep.
10. Three Primary colours: blue, yellow, red, with 3 groups of colours: Primary, secondary and tertiary.
11. Three forms of verb: was, is and will (past, present and future).
12. Yoga is the connection of 3 elements: yourself, people and nature.
13. Human pregnancy is also divided in to 3 trimesters, first, second and third.
14. There are 3 kingdoms in nature: animal, mineral and vegetable kingdoms.
15. Three interlocked Borromean Rings as symbol of "strength in unity", used for centuries. Divide any one ring; the other two will fall apart.
16. Borromean Rings principle is used in

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nanotechnology, mathematics, chemistry, physics, biology, material science, engineering etc. It is the Logo of International Mathematics Union.

17. *Three pillars of sustainability*-environment, economics and social [31].
18. The Three M's of Statistical science: Mode, Median, Mean- commonly used in Practice, making it more manageable.

B: Spirituality and Religion

1. Three attributes of God: omniscient, omnipresent and omnipotent;
2. Three is perfect number. Nature of all human beings is three-fold: body, mind, spirit.
3. Principal of trinity found in all world religions:
4. In ancient mankind history, number 3 has great importance in every religion [9].

Buddhism [8]a. *Buddha*'s Three jewels i.e. b. Trinetra (teacher), Dharma (teachings), Sangha (community). c. Three sticks of incense offered at shrines in Vietnam. d. Path to Enlightenment: morality, meditation and wisdom.

Christianity [9] a. Trinity: One God in 3 divine persons: The Father, The Son, The Holy Spirit. b. Number 3 is repeated 467 times in Bible, meaning completeness. c. Biblical Magi; the three wise men.

Hinduism [10] a. Tridev: Brahma, Vishnu, Mahesh. b. Three parts of vedic prayer "lead me from darkness to light, from ignorance to knowledge, from death to immortality. c. Mandukya Upanishad has 12 verses, adding up to $1+2=3$. d. Lord Shiva's weapon is Trishul, HE is called Trinetra and trikaldarshi also. If number 3 is rotated right, it looks like Trishul. Bael patras (group of 3 leaves considered as singles), offered to Lord Shiva, e. Symbol AUM, consisting of 3 letters, its figure apparently looks as 3. f. Trilokas as Paatal, Prithvi and Akash.

g. In Yogasanas, figure of 3 is commonly seen in so many asanas. h. Triveni: sangam of 3 rivers: Ganga,, Yamuna and Saraswati at Prayagraj.

h. Triphala is a common Ayurvedic combination of 3 herbs. i. Tribhuvan: Common Hindu name: having knowledge of 3 worlds. j. There are 108 beads ($1+0+8=9\div3=3$) in a prayer Rosary. k. Teej or Akshaya tritiya: important festival of northern and western India.

Sikhism [11]: a. 3 pillars of Sikhism of Guru Nanak Dev Ji: Naam Japo (meditate on God), kirat karo (earn honestly by hard work) and Wand Chhako (share and consume).

b. Ek Omkar looks like number 3 extended upwards from left side, symbolizing one God.

Islam [12]: a. Wudu- practice of 3 times washing hands, face etc

b. Allah written in Arabic also looks like 3, facing upwards and Muslims pray with palms facing upwards. In Arabic, first plural number is 2, meaning plentiful.

Zoroastrian [7]: Three ethical principles: think good, speak good and act good.

Judaism [13]: Religion of Jews, number 3 denotes completeness [8]

Pharaohs [51]: polytheistic religious beliefs- Egyptian pyramids are triangular.

Political/ Governance:

1. Three pillars of democracy: Government of the people, by the people, for the people.
2. Indian National flag is tricolor.
3. Three lions are the emblem of India, depicting power, courage and confidence.
4. Three wings of armed Forces are Army. Air Force, Navy.
5. India was declared a republic on 26-1-1950, celebrated since then as its Republic Day. Tricolor is unfurled with a 21 GUN salute, both totaling and making $(2+6+1+1+9+5+0=24/8=3$, and $2+1=3$)

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6. USA national flag also has 3 colours- white, blue, red, while it has 50 stars plus 15 stripes: $5+0+1+3= 6+3= 9/3= 3$ [37].
7. Philippines National flag has 3 colours with one white triangular portion, having printed a sign of Sun and 3 stars around it at the hoist side [38].
8. Australian National Flag is also tricolored [41].

Social/ Cultural Age old traditions in daily life of humanity, all over the world.

1. Three monkeys? symbol: hear no evil, see no evil and speak no evil, in India.
2. To praise or encourage somebody, we say- three cheers and hip, hip hurray.
3. Baa baa black sheep had three bags full, a nursery rhyme.
4. Prizes in schools/colleges and sports are also three: Gold, Silver and Bronze.
5. Best of 3 chances in a draw game
6. Three parts of any event: beginning, interval and end.
7. International YOGA day, is celebrated every year on 21 June ($2+1+6= 9/3=3$), was proclaimed by United Nations on 11.12.2014= $30/10=3$ [34]. Maharishi Patanjali, the Father of Yoga has 18 letters: $1+8= 9/3= 3$.
8. Year of Swami Vivekananda's historic lectures at world parliament of religions is 1893, adding up to $1+8+9+3= 21$ ($2+1$)= 3.
9. Popular social movies, Taare Zameen Par and Three Idiots had 3 words.
10. Three parts of the day: morning, afternoon and evening.
11. Three usual meals: breakfast, lunch and dinner.
12. Three stages of human life: childhood, adulthood and old age.
13. In cricket, there are 3 stumps to make a wicket.
14. Famous 3Ws and 3 Ws Oval: West Indies ace cricketers and monumental ground: Wikipedia en.wikipedia.org › wiki › [24].
15. 3D street art: (<https://www.hongkiat.com/blog/absolutely-stunning-3d-street-art-paintings/>)
16. Thousands of threesomes and trios of daily use in human society all over world [8].
17. The Three Musketeers - Wikipedia en.wikipedia.org › wiki ›
18. Famous 3; The Best Trios and Threesomes of All Time - Ranker www.ranker.com › best-trios-of-all-time › lauren-slocum.
19. Python 3 programming language in a computer science course [11]
20. Famous fairy tales we grew with: three little pigs etc [14]
21. There are hundreds of triads in kaleidoscopic fields listed in Wikipedia [19].
22. Private Club 33 of Walt Disney, at Disneyland, lounges at 3 locations [28].
23. The **3** Seventh Avenue Express [2] is a rapid transit subway service in New York [29].
24. Sardar Sarovar Dam, second largest concrete dam of world reached its maximum height and capacity on 15. 9. 2019, totaling 36, a multiple of 3 [30].
25. World's tallest "Statue of unity" (Sardar Patel's) is 597 feet high ($5+9+7=2+1$) [35].
26. SUN has 3 letters only. Sun and 3 stars logos and stickers are very popular [36]
27. World Ocean Day was introduced in 1992 by United Nations ($1+9+9+2$), For 2020 Theme of this day on 8th June is the global movement to protect 30 % of Our blue planet by 2030, a critical need, named as 30x30 [39,40].
28. Indian Express News, 23.7.2020, 18 years ($1+8=9/3=3$), deaf and dumb Abdul Latif studying at a famous special School of Patiala, traces his family of Farrukhabad (U.P) after 10 years, through internet during lockdown, with a happy reunion [42].
29. Mahatma Gandhi's Date of birth: 2.10.1869 also totals- $2+10+1+8+6+9= 27/9= 3$.
30. Common 3 words expressions: do's and don'ts, black and white, pros and cons,

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tried and tested, by and large, ins and outs, haves and have nots, all is well, now or never, against all odds, believe in yourself, be a giver, happy new year, happy frienda day and all such days, How are you?, I am good etc. [49,50].

Medical Systems:

1. *Ayurveda*: Tridosha: Vaat, Pitt, Kaff to be in balance for healthy body/mind complex.
2. *Homeopathy*: Hahnemann's 3 miasms: Psora, syphilis and sycosis cause all Diseases.
3. Sidha system- 3 cause of diseases in Siddha Concept of Vatham, Pitham & kapham.
4. *Allopathy*: This is a common concept to validate three consecutive batches in pharmaceuticals [10].
5. *Unani* system: 3 kinds of Faculties/Powers (Quwa), according to Unani medicine: psychic (natural) power, power of metabolism and power of reproduction [13].
6. TDS or TID i.e. three times a day is a common mode of prescription.
7. *Orthopaedics*: Trimalleolar fracture of ankle and others.

Author's Personal life

1. Author's name, Rattan Lal Mittal, has 15 letters, adding up to $1+5= 6/2=3$.
2. Lucky date of author's marriage 26.2.1967 ($2+6+2+1+9+6+7= 33/11=3$).
3. My wife, Dr Radha Rani Mittal, also having 15 letters in her name, a renowned Dermatologist, also Dr. B.C. Roy National Awardee, great motive force for the author.
4. I have three daughters, helping and motivating me in this great research venture.
5. Three grand-daughters, helping me with silent prayers.

The entire write up, as above, shows that number 3 is the most frequented number in

every aspect of every human life, including the author, all over the world, from birth till death.

Number 3 and Clubfoot Research Intimacy:

It was unbelievable, when I discovered recently in a publication [58] that number 3 had an amazing 11 repetitions, nine times in author's clubfoot research and twice in personal life. This motivated me for further research in this area and surprisingly, enormous material was discovered. I could discover 12 more in clubfoot research and 3 more in personal life, raising the tally to 26 times. Author researched in extreme congenital clubfoot deformities, which are highly prevalent in low and middle income countries (LMICs) with 80 % of global population and an unexplored, neglected area. Author invented, landmark, new surgical techniques, in need based 3 phases; which were cost effective, and highly satisfying in looks as well as long term functional results. Number 3 has been found to be a lucky number for the author, with innumerable periodic, National/International awards/ rewards, Global presentations/ publications, including a recent, world class, invited *Clubfoot Book* [52-59]. *Twenty one times Repetition of number 3, in this research, some scientific and others amazing truths, has been in perfect sequence, as given below:-*.

1. Anatomical dissection of 15 clubfeet in stillborn foetuses ($15/ 5 = 3$).
2. *Ttrimorphic* (Three grades) clubfoot deformities.
3. Invented *triple* surgical skin expansion techniques.
4. In need based 3 phases, i.e. for Grade 1, Grade 2 and Grade 3 extreme deformities in distinct timeline, as more and more rigid deformities presented for correction.
5. *First ever use of 3 plastic surgery procedures in an orthopaedic surgical procedure*.
6. *First ever, 3DX3 mega expansion of fasciocutaneous chamber* i.e. 3 procedures

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- and each in 3D, obtaining maximum possible expansion. A small room with too many people with no leg space, made adequately roomier, giving comfort, stretched out legs and free all round movements
7. *Combining all three plastic surgery procedures in single incision* by triple surgical skin expansion to obtain maximum fascio-cutaneous chamber expansion (Fusion 3-in-1, all inclusive, surgical concept), .
 8. *Three U-TURNS* for this research: An Alumni of Government Medical College Patiala, author moved to Delhi, India's Capital, in January 1961 for greener pastures and had *first U-turn to Patiala*; in July 1961; *second U-turn to Patiala* from Rohtak (Haryana State) in 1966 after being out of Patiala for about 4 years, and *third U-turn*, recently in 2018, on being designated as *Emeritus Professor* at Government Medical College Patiala due to this passion,, 23 years post retirement, to contribute to research, academics and free surgeries.
 9. As a passionate researcher *Indian Council of Medical Research National Award (for skeletal fluorosis) dated 09.03.1992*: $(9+3+1+9+9+2=33)$ $(3+3=6/2=3)$; which acted as motivation, post superannuation to pursue Clubfoot research in second and third phases.
 10. *Dr. B.C.Roy National Award on 11.07.1995* $(1+1+0+7+1+9+9+5=3+3=6/2=3)$ and club foot research contributing, immensely, to this award and vice versa, i.e., this award also motivated to continue clubfoot research, bringing more awards/ rewards..
 11. *First ever, all THREE original research awards of Indian Orthopaedic Association*: Silver jubilee in 1988, Golden in 2013 and Diamond in 2108, for a single research.
 12. First ever *Hat Trick* (3 Awards in line by Indian Orthopaedic Association), as above.
 13. *Golden Jubilee Award on 06.12.2013* $(6+1+2+2+0+1+3=15)$ $(1+5=6/2=3)$.
 14. Written an invited book on clubfoot, titled "CLUBFOOT - A Comprehensive Approach (*past, Present and Future*)" for Taylor & Francis, a premier Global Publisher, with *final go ahead and intimating mail dated 19. 1. 2017* $(1+9+1+2+0+1+7=21)$ and $2+1=3$ for contract signing, as auspicious date, coinciding with Swami Vivekananda's birthday Kundli TITHI as per Hindu Calendar (from publisher's trail of mails). The Book has been dedicated to Swami Ji, my inspiration (How and Why given in book's preface and introduction).
 15. *Three honours at Coimbatore (T.N INDIA) at 2018 IOACON*: i. comprehensive lecture on this research; ii. Diamond Jubilee Research Award and iii. CLUBFOOT BOOK Release.
 16. Date of BOOK release on *29th November 2018*, at the Annual IOACON: $2+9+1+1+2+0+1+8=24/8=6/2=3$.
 17. *CLUBFOOT Book's name has three parts*: "CUBFOOT - A Comprehensive Approach (PAST, Present and Future)", and also *having all three eras of time*: past, present and Future, an amazing truth.
 18. *This name of the Book was finalised on 19. 1. 2017* i.e. $1+9+1+2+0+1+7=2+1=3$, as recorded in the trail of mails with the publisher.
 19. *ISBN of Book 9781138083738*: totals 3: $9+7+8+1+1+3+8+0+8+3+7+3+8=6+6=12/4=20$
 20. *Octopus Clubfoot, world's first, with this new Exotic name in literature, given by the author, has 15 letters*, multiple of 3, with many firsts. The date of this surgery

incidentally also comes to, $2+1+9+2+0+1+9=24/8=3$. There was media coverage of this case also (Figures 2,3).

Figure 1(a-d): Free teaching and research oriented surgery of right foot as Emeritus Professor in a 17 years old female, under-corrected and relapsed after 2 previous surgeries, Grade3 High extreme deformity right foot; print media, The Tribune coverage (b), incision marks at 3 weeks and correction seen at 3 weeks (c) and excellent correction by triple surgical mega-correction without any bony fusion at about 7 months follow up and patient happily walking about (d).

Figure 2(a-e): Octopus Clubfoot, World’s first most extreme deformity (a); An exotic Left foot print (b), Corrected by 3-in-1 single incision with added fillet flap for an excellent correction (triangle of v-y-plasty seen (c), excellent correction without any bony fusion (d) and normal foot print (e). Acknowledgements- Reprinted/ adapted by kind courtesy Springer Nature and Copyright clearance centre of RightsLink . From author’s own published article; Mittal RL. *Trimorphic extreme clubfoot deformities and their management by triple surgical skin expanders-DOLAR, OLARZ and DOLAR-E (evidence based mega- correction without arthrodesis)*. DOI 10.1007/s00264-017-3741-6. As well as kind Courtesy of Taylor & Francis group (CRS Press) adopted from author’s own book *Clubfoot-A comprehensive approach past present & future: 1st edition*, by Dr. R L Mittal. Dec.2018. ISBN 9781138083738.

Figure 3(a-d): AS 7MC high grade 3 extreme deformity with lateral callosity on sole (a) extending towards dorsum b), corrected by mega fasciocutaneous expansion by triple surgical skin incision and 3 partial thickness grafts, without any bony fusion (c). Excellent correction at 6 weeks, showing evidence of healing scars of 3 skin grafts and a K-wire at great toe, on medial side of foot and (d and e) Foot seen from medial side with excellent correction, standing and walking about normally at 5 months follow up. Acknowledgements- Figure.3- Reprinted/ adapted by kind courtesy for author’s own publication Mittal RL. *Each Clubfoot is Different, Mother of All Clubfoot Innovations (An Incredible*

Unity in Diversity, with Cure-All, Fusion 4-in-1 Surgical Concept) Ortho Res Online J. 7(1). OPROJ. 000655. 2020. DOI: 10.31031/OPROJ.2020.07.000655.

Discussion/Conclusion:

If there is any number, worth mentioning a million times, it is number 3. This symbolizes Jupiter with goodness, sacrifice, purest love, and eternal giver to humanity, the most significant of all, the most beneficial planet, called the “Guru” or the Spiritual Master. Number 3 is the first plural number by adding the very first 2 numbers, 1 and 2 [33]. Planet JUPITER has numerous other good attributes: original, curious, creative, energetic, hardworking, social and many more [1]. *There is even a book of all threes* on every subject: art, science, mathematics, history, politics, sports, literature, idioms, music, quotations, entertainment, language, religion, nature, food, including a video demonstration [47].

There is unlimited more material on Google search engine. Traditions were laid down in human history, one after another, since ages, all over the Globe, linking every aspect of daily life with number 3. To prove it further, the most prestigious and highest intellectual INTERNATIONAL AWARD, [25]. *First Miss Universe Pageant* was started on 28th June 1952, a multiple of number 3 [26] and the [27,44]. In *North Pole*, Alaska’s winter in ice, *three great things to do* are: 1- Celebrating Christmas in ice; 2- Watching dancing (Aurora) lights in the sky and 3- Local eats, besides this *Google search site* is dated 06.01.2018, a multiple of 3 [45]. *National ocean day of*

Japan is celebrated on 3rd Monday in July every year [46]. *National flags Of India, USA and Philippines* in the *northern hemisphere* are tricoloured and of *Australia* in the *Southern hemisphere* is also tricoloured. Considering it in medical sciences: Orthopaedics- there are some common examples: a) *Trimalleolar fracture of ankle*, wherein besides the fracture of 2 malleoli, the posterior part of the tibial plafond has been named as third malleolus, which it is not. It has been named so just to bring in number 3 and make it catchy; b) *Bankart’s triad* in recurrent dislocation shoulder, c) *Unhappy triad knee injury*. In *human anatomy*; there are 43 *triangular images* [32]. In Dermatology, there is a *Triple response* of Lewis, inflammatory in nature [43]. There must be many more in other branches of medical sciences.

“Human mind is a store house of infinite energy, Dis + Cover it”, “you are the creator of your own destiny” and “Take up an idea, think it, dream it, live with it till realized” [21]. Therefore, persistent hard work on a single problem is the key to success. “Genius is one percent inspiration and ninety-nine percent perspiration” [22].

That is how the author was led to, single track clubfoot research more than 50 years ago, in January 1961 to be exact. Motivated by periodical awards/ rewards, it is still

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continuing. It started with number 3 (dissection of 15 stillborn infant's clubfeet ($1+5 = 6/2 = 3$). Sixteen were the largest number of dissections reported in the world literature, till then [52]. Author could, at least, have equaled or exceeded the largest series of the world, if one or more were found. However, this had to be multiple of three because of its unique importance for the author.

The research remained dominated with unparalleled repetition of number 3, 21 times till now and 5 times in author's personal life, with numerous national and International awards and rewards, proving the strength of number 3. Proof of a good pudding lies in eating which has been served.

Innumerable examples have been discovered from Google search and many more may still be there unsearched. More amazing truths, with a tenacious base in all religions, social and cultural life of human society, from birth till end, have been discovered on extensive Google search.

To conclude

It is purely scientific not only in clubfoot research, but in all branches of science, medical and non- medical. There are myriad amazing truths having scientific basis. This article is only a tip of the iceberg, or a drop in the ocean; on Mother Earth Planet and beyond. There must be limitless more material and one can go on and on and on.... There are some, amazing/unprecedented truths also, *proving once again "Truth is stranger than fiction"*. It has to be, because truth happens of its own and is not under our control; while fiction is the creation of human mind, so controlled by it.

References

Part-I

- 1 <https://www.lucky-name-numerology.com/name-numerology-9.html>
- 2 <https://sites.google.com/site/numberopedia/number3inscience>
3. <https://futureandcosmos.blogspot.com/2014/01/nature-seems-to-love-number-three.html>
4. <https://scienceblog.com/2805/chemists-make-molecular-interlocked-rings/>
5. Vijith Kumar, Tullio Pilati, Giancarlo Terraneo, et al. 2016. Halogen bonded Borromean networks by design: topology invariance and metric tuning in a library of multi-component systems. Ref.: shorturl.at/fLPU1
6. A link between quantum mechanics and topology implies the existence of an entirely new state of matter. And physicists have already found the first example. December 16, 2010. Ref.: shorturl.at/istIP
7. <https://mysticalnumbers.com/number-3/> in science and other areas.
8. <https://in.search.yahoo.com/search?p=budhism+and+number+3&fr=yfp-t&fp=1&toggl=1&cop=mss&ei=UTF-8>.
9. <https://www.biblestudy.org/bibleref/meaning-of-numbers-in-bible/3.html>
10. Importance and Significance of Number 3 in Hinduism. 2018. Ref.: shorturl.at/aFLV8
11. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Three_pillars_of_Sikhism
12. <https://islam.stackexchange.com/questions/25402/why-does-the-number-3-repeats-itself-in-islam>.
13. <http://www.betemunah.org/three.html>
14. <https://www.ancient-code.com/ancient-knowledge-the-secret-importance-behind-the-number-3/>.
15. Three Consecutive Batches for Validation in Pharmaceuticals
www.pharmaguideline.com/2013/08/three...

Awesome repetition of number 3 in correction of *Trimorphic Extreme Clubfoot Deformities by Triple Surgical Skin Expansion (An Evolutionary, Multifaceted, Scientific Perspective)*

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16. <https://codehs.com/course/python3/overview.1>
17. www.who.int > BenchmarksforTraininginUnaniMedicine > Origin and principles of Unani medicine - World Health.
18. <https://www.ukandoo.com/power-of-3-in-marketing/>
19. https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/stephen_hawking_627142#:
20. <https://due.com/blog/swami-vivekananda-take-up-one-idea/>
21. <https://www.goalcast.com/2017/05/11/thomas-edison-quotes-motivate-never-quit/>
22. <https://mysticalnumbers.com/number-3/>
23. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triad>.
24. The Nobel Peace Prize Medal. Ref.: shorturl.at/myzDR
25. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Miss_Universe_1952.
26. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cricket_World_Cup_Trophy.
27. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Club_33
28. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/3_\(New_York_City_Subway_service\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/3_(New_York_City_Subway_service)).
29. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sardar_Sarovar_Dam.
30. <https://www.thwink.org/sustain/glossary/ThreePillarsOfSustainability.htm>.
31. <https://in.pinterest.com/iqubali/triangles-in-anatomy/>
32. Number 3 in Numerology – The Heart of Humanity. 2009. Ref.: shorturl.at/hnvCQ
33. <https://www.indiacelebrating.com/events/international-day-of-yoga/>
34. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Statue_of_Unity.
35. <https://www.redbubble.com/shop/3+stars+and+a+sun+stickers>
36. Former Director, Flag Research Center, Winchester, et al. 1898. Flag of the Philippines. Ref.: shorturl.at/wDKLW
37. Marc Leepson. 1960. Flag of the United States of America. Ref.: shorturl.at/tzOU0
38. <https://worldoceanday.org/take-action/petition>
39. <https://www.timeanddate.com/holidays/un/oceans-day>.
40. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flag_of_Australia.
41. <file:///C:/Users/pc/Downloads/nimf-ie-chandigarh-23-07-2020.pdf>
42. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triple_response_of_Lewis.
43. <https://phys.org/news/2020-06-south-pole-faster-rest-earth.html>
44. <https://spotofteatravels.com/2018/01/06/3-of-my-favorite-things-to-do-in-north-pole-alaska-during-the-winter/>
45. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marine_Day
46. <https://www.bookofthrees.com/what-comes-in-threes/>
47. The Three M's of Statistics: Mode, Median, Mean. 2010. Ref.: shorturl.at/opIY6
48. <https://www.english-at-home.com/vocabulary/three-word-phrases/>.
49. <https://www.rootreport.com/short-three-word-quotes/>
50. <http://www.toureygypt.net/featurestories/pyramidreligion.htm>

PART II:

51. Mittal RL, Makhni SS, Sidhu GS. 1981. Morbid anatomy of congenital clubfoot. *Ind J Ortho*. 15: 129-135.
52. Mittal RL. 1987. The surgical management of resistant clubfoot by rotation skin flap and extensive soft tissue release. *Int Orthop*. 11: 189-92. Ref.: shorturl.at/owxR4
53. Mittal RL, Sekhon AS, Singh G. et al. 1993. The prevalence of congenital orthopaedic anomalies in a rural community. *International Orthopaedics*. Ref.: shorturl.at/eAMNX
54. Mittal RL. 2014. Obstinate clubfoot with triple plus dislocation. *J Foot Ankle Surg (Asia-Pacific)*. 1: 72-77. Ref.: shorturl.at/oDF39
55. Mittal RL. 2018. Trimorphic extreme clubfoot deformities and their management by triple surgical skin expanders- *DOLAR, DOLARZ and DOLARZ-E* (evidence based mega

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Extreme Clubfoot Deformities by *Triple* Surgical Skin Expansion
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36811/cjo.2020.110002>

CJO: August-2020: Page No: 01-11

corrections without arthrodesis) Online first in April 2018 and then as print version International Orthopaedics (SICOT). 42: 1297-1306. Ref.: shorturl.at/fhH47

56. Mittal RL. 2018. CLUBFOOT - A Comprehensive Approach (Past, Present and Future); 1st Edition, 178 pages, 45 illustrations. Taylor and Francis (CRS Press), USA. ISBN No 9781138083738. Ref.: shorturl.at/dmJK2
57. Mittal RL. 2019. Octopus Clubfoot Rediscovered - World's First Exotic Case - A Neglected, Triple Axes Rotational, Grade 3 Extreme Deformity: Corrected by, Unparalleled, 4-In-1 Mega Surgical Skin Expansion from Crooked to ROZY Foot. Ortho Res Online J. 6.
58. Mittal RL. 2019. Feet Also Need Cosmetic/ Plastic Surgery for Good Looks (A New Perspective) World's First, Graded, Mega Skin Expansion by Fusion 4-In-1, Correcting, All-Inclusive, Extreme Clubfoot Deformities- A Game Changer. J. Dermatol & Skin Sci.1: 8-17. Ref.: shorturl.at/pAF13
59. Mittal RL. 2020. Each Clubfoot is Different, Mother of All Clubfoot Innovations (An Incredible Unity in Diversity, with Cure-All, Fusion 4-in-1 Surgical Concept). Ortho Res Online J. 7.